

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**MANAGEMENT AND CLINICAL PRESENTATION OF
ADENOMATOID ODONTOGENIC TUMOR****¹Dr. Shaista Aziz, ²Dr. Fatima, ³Dr. Fariha Sameen, ⁴Dr. Mohsin Majeed, ⁵Dr. Sara Izhar**
Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan^{1,2,3,4,5}**Article Received:** December 2018 **Accepted:** February 2019 **Published:** March 2019**Abstract:****Objective:** To document the clinical presentation and treatment protocols of the adenomatoid odontogenic tumor in the oral cavity.**Study design:** A descriptive study.**Location and Duration:** In the Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Department of Nishtar Institute of Dentistry (NID), Multan for One-year duration from November 2017 to October 2018.**Methods:** The sampling technique was deliberate. Six cases of AOT were recorded. The age range was 11-16 years (mean 13.8 years) and there were 4 (66.6%) cases in males.**Results:** Maxillary involvement was present in five patients (83%). Only one case had a complaint of the mandible (left side).**Conclusion:** AOT is a relatively rare lesion, especially in adolescents. It should be applied at an early stage to prevent damage to adjacent teeth.**Key words:** canine, odontogenic, adenomatoid, maxilla, tumor.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Shaista Aziz,**
Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Shaista Aziz et al., *Management And Clinical Presentation Of Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(03).

INTRODUCTION:

Adenomatoid odontogenic tumor (AOT) is a non-invasive benign (hamartomatous) odontogenic lesion with slow but continuous growth. It is relatively rare and accounts for approximately 3-7% of all odontogenic tumors [1-3]. The lesion originates from the odontogenic epithelium (enamel or dental laminae residues) which have inductive effect on odontogenic ectomesenchyme and subsequent production of dentinoid material. AOT is predominantly found in young patients and women, most commonly associated with a permanent tooth in the maxilla that has not emerged in most cases. However, it is documented in the molar region [4-6]. Radiographically, AOT is often seen as a limited unilocular radiolucency and may be most often associated with an unerupted tooth, which is a canine mostly. In the microscopic examination, the lesion usually appears as a central (follicular, extrafollicular) or peripheral entity [7-9]. AOT

responds well to protective enucleation and relapses are rarely reported.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was performed in the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery of Nishtar Institute of Dentistry (NID), Multan for One year duration from November 2017 to October 2018. This is a type of descriptive study with purposive sampling. Six patients showed AOT characteristics. Perioperative routine study was performed and an incisional biopsy was performed in all cases to confirm the diagnosis of AOT following informed consent. All lesions reported in this series were treated with enucleation by conservative surgery. The diagnosis of AOT was confirmed by excision biopsies.

RESULTS:

Six adenomatoid odontogenic tumor cases were recorded during the study period (Table 1).

TABLE 1: CLINICAL PRESENTATION OF ADENOMATOID ODONTOGENIC TUMOR

Case No.	Age	Sex	Site	Presentation
1	16	F	Right Maxilla	Extended from the distal aspect of the lateral incisor to the mesial aspect of the first molar. Canine and premolars failed to erupt
2	13	M	Right Maxilla	Extended from the distal aspect of central incisor to the mesial aspect of the 2 nd premolar. Lateral incisor, canine and 1st premolar unerupted.
3	14	M	Right Maxilla	Extended from the distal aspect of lateral incisor to the mesial aspect of the Pt premolar. Canine unerupted
4	12	M	Left Maxilla	Involved the canine tooth alone, which was still high and unerupted.
5	13	M	Left Mandible	Extended from the distal aspect of the lateral incisor to the distal aspect of the canine. Canine failed to erupt.
6	15	F	Right Maxilla	Extended from the distal aspect of central incisor to the mesial aspect of the 2 nd premolar. Lateral incisor, canine and 1st premolar unerupted.

The age range was 11-16 years (mean 13.8 years) and there were four cases (66.6%) in males. Maxillary involvement was observed in five patients (83%) and four patients with the right case involvement. Only one case had a complaint of the mandible (left side). In all cases in this series, multiple teeth adjacent to the lesion did not erupt.

Fig. 1. Extra-oral view of the patient

Fig. 2. Intra-oral view of the lesion; note the absence of teeth in the involved region

Case No. 1 (Figure 1 and Figure 2). In three cases, evidence of radiographic calcification within the tumor was evident. Six patients had intra-osseous and follicular variants in histopathology.

After a one-year follow-up period, no recurrence was observed in any of the six patients after surgical enucleation.

DISCUSSION:

This is probably the first series of AOTs reported from Pakistan. In this study, M: F ratio was 2: 1, unlike the reported female preference. However, the incidence of AOT was reported to be higher in males in other studies¹⁰⁻¹². Clinical-radiographic features of AOT can simulate various lesions including dentigerous cysts, e.g. calcification of odontogenic cysts, calcification of odontogenic epithelial tumors, etc. Discriminant tests using radiography to separate tumors from cystic lesions of the oral cavity have been described, but this approach may have significant potential for error. MRI findings are more useful in this regard¹³⁻¹⁴. The pigmentation of melanin was rarely reported in AOT and was interestingly apparent in the specimen extracted in one of the cases (Figure 4). Histopathology confirmed the presence of melanin in the tumor epithelium¹⁵. However, the exact histopathogenesis of melanin pigmentation could not be determined. Recurrence is usually not reported after conservative surgical enucleation, and the author received similar postoperative results in this series.

CONCLUSION:

AOT is a rare lesion especially seen in adolescents. Given the potential for continuous growth, it should

be managed at an early stage to prevent damage to adjacent teeth.

REFERENCES:

1. Coura, Bruna Pizziolo, Vanessa Fátima Bernardes, Sílvia Ferreira de Sousa, Josiane Alves França, Núbia Braga Pereira, Hélder Antônio Rebelo Pontes, Aline Carvalho Batista et al. "KRAS mutations drive adenomatoid odontogenic tumor and are independent of clinicopathological features." *Modern Pathology* (2019): 1.
2. La Monaca, Gerardo, Nicola Pranno, Cira Rosaria Tiziana di Gioia, Giorgio Pompa, Iole Voza, and Maria Paola Cristalli. "Surgical Management of Extrafollicular Variant of Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor in the Maxillary Posterior Region." *Case Reports in Dentistry* 2019 (2019).
3. Chrcanovic, Bruno Ramos, and Ricardo Santiago Gomez. "Adenomatoid odontogenic tumor: an updated analysis of the cases reported in the literature." *Journal of Oral Pathology & Medicine* (2019).
4. Fazeli, Shoreh R., Kamyar R. Giglou, Mahmoud L. Soliman, Waleed H. Ezzat, Andrew Salama, and Qing Zhao. "Calcifying Epithelial Odontogenic (Pindborg) Tumor in a Child: A Case Report and Literature Review." *Head and neck pathology*(2019): 1-7.
5. Siriwardena BS, Crane H, O'Neill N, Abdelkarim R, Brierley DJ, Franklin CD, Farthing PM, Speight PM, Hunter KD. Odontogenic tumors and lesions treated in a single specialist oral and maxillofacial pathology

- unit in the United Kingdom in 1992–2016. Oral surgery, oral medicine, oral pathology and oral radiology. 2019 Feb 1;127(2):151-66.
6. de Arruda, José Alcides A., Lucas G. Abreu, Leni Verônica de O. Silva, Lauren F. Schuch, João Luiz GC Monteiro, Diego Antônio C. Arantes, Adriana Aparecida S. da Costa et al. "Calcifying epithelial odontogenic tumours: collaborative study of 32 cases and review of literature." *Oral diseases* 25, no. 1 (2019): 192-205.
 7. Bussari, Smita, Samantha M. Thakur, Ajit V. Koshy, and Amisha A. Shah. "Dentinogenic ghost cell tumor—A case report and review of literature." *Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology* 23, no. 4 (2019): 66.
 8. Pahlevan, Roozbeh, Farnaz Keyhanlou, Sahar Fazel, and Fatemeh Shahsavari. "Keratocystic odontogenic tumor associated with impacted maxillary third molar extending to the antrum: A challenging diagnosis." *Human Pathology: Case Reports* 15 (2019): 59-63.
 9. Diniz, Marina Gonçalves, Josiane Alves França, Fabrício AS Vilas-Boas, Fabrício Tinôco Alvim de Souza, George Adrian Calin, Ricardo Santiago Gomez, Sílvia Ferreira de Sousa, and Carolina Cavalieri Gomes. "The long noncoding RNA KIAA0125 is upregulated in ameloblastomas." *Pathology-Research and Practice* 215, no. 3 (2019): 466-469.
 10. Chrcanovic, Bruno Ramos, Mauro Henrique Nogueira Guimarães Abreu, Peter A. Brennan, and Ricardo Santiago Gomez. "Some methodological issues on the review of pathologic lesions and conditions." *Journal of Oral Pathology & Medicine* (2019).
 11. Takahashi, Saori, Yayoi Idaira, Toru Sato, Yoshinobu Asada, and Yoichi Nakagawa. "Unicystic Ameloblastoma in a Child Treated with a Combination of Conservative Surgery and Orthodontic Treatment: A Case Report." *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry* (2019).
 12. Koc, Nagihan, Hatice Boyacioglu Dogru, L. Berna Cagirankaya, Sema Dural, and Paul F. van der Stelt. "CBCT assessment of gubernacular canals in relation to eruption disturbance and pathologic condition associated with impacted/unerupted teeth." *Oral surgery, oral medicine, oral pathology and oral radiology* 127, no. 2 (2019): 175-184.
 13. Dokova, Anastassia F., Sindhura Anamali, Renee Ismail, Jeffrey A. Lindhout, Erika Benavides, Larry B. Salzman, and Theodora E. Danciu. "A pediatric patient with multiple radiolucencies impeding normal tooth eruption." *The Journal of the American Dental Association* 150, no. 1 (2019): 70-75.
 14. Kim, Jue Young, Jinsun Kim, Shadavlonjid Bazarsad, In-Ho Cha, Sung-Won Cho, and Jin Kim. "Bcl-2 is a prognostic marker and its silencing inhibits recurrence in ameloblastomas." *Oral diseases* (2019).
 15. TIWARI, R., RAVIKUMAR, A.J. and DUBEY, A., 2019. Cone Beam Computed Tomography Analysis of Canalis Sinuosus in Association with an Osteolytic Lesion of Maxilla: A Case Report and Review of Literature. *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research*, 13(2).